

Gender Considerations in the Measurement of Climate Change Anxiety: A Cross-Sectional Study in British Columbia, Canada

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ABSTRACT

Globally, the impacts of climate change disproportionately impact women and gender non-binary people (non-binary). Few studies have examined gender differences in climate change anxiety (CCA). Methods: This study examines gender differences in CCA among women, men, and non-binary people living in British Columbia, Canada. Participants were recruited between May and December 2021 using online advertisements. Results: Among 1,260 participants, 21.9% (n = 138/631) of men, 49.5% (n = 257/519) of women, and 54.9% (n = 28/51) of non-binary participants, had moderate/high CCA scores. Men were less likely to report difficulty concentrating (p < 0.001), crying (p < 0.001), or responding to climate change by writing down and analyzing their thoughts (p < 0.001). Demographically adjusted models showed higher CCA among women (aOR = 2.17, 95% CI [1.65-2.85]) and non-binary participants (aOR = 2.70, 95% CI [1.43-5.13]) relative to men. When also adjusting for generalized psychological distress, the elevated effect among women remained significant (aOR = 1.52, 95% CI [1.14-2.04]), while the effect among non-binary participants was no longer significant (aOR = 1.67, 95% CI: [0.86-3.26]). Conclusions: Despite differences in generalized psychological distress, women and non-binary people likely experience a disproportionate burden of CCA. Further research is needed to understand the underlying mechanisms and potential mental health supports for individuals struggling with CCA across the gender spectrum.

Keywords: Gender differences; climate change; anxiety; climate change anxiety

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INTRODUCTION

Climate change is contributing to a wide range of adverse health impacts, including those related to food and water security, housing stability, frailty, stress, and physical injury (Cianconi et al., 2020). These impacts vary considerably across genders, with unique pathways of harm experienced by men, women, and gender non-binary (non-binary) individuals (Desai & Zhang, 2021; van Daalen et al., 2020).

The mental health impacts of climate change vary by gender. For example, women experience climate emotions, including worry, frustration, and helplessness, at higher rates than men (Clayton et al., 2023; Galway & Beery, 2022). Women also have higher levels of awareness of the potential impacts of climate change (Davidson & Haan, 2012). Previous studies have pointed to a need for support and resources to help cope with these emotions and mitigate the risk of mental health consequences (Galway & Beery, 2022).

Gender differences in the mental health responses to climate change are shaped by traditional gender roles and societal expectations. For men, these roles often emphasize strength and emotional stoicism (Addis & Mahalik, 2003). As a result, men may suppress feelings of anxiety or distress related to climate change, making them less likely to seek support or adopt coping strategies (Addis & Mahalik, 2003). Research also indicates that many men, particularly those who are older, white, and conservative, report feeling less vulnerable to the effects of climate change (Marshall et al., 2006). However, men directly affected by climate-related disasters, such as drought, may experience heightened stress, anxiety, anger, isolation, and, in some cases, an increased risk of suicide as men feel their masculinity is challenged (Enarson & Pease, 2016). In contrast, traditional gender roles for women emphasize caregiving and nurturing, which may foster a heightened sense of responsibility for addressing climate change and its impacts (McCright, 2010). Women are also often underrepresented in climate change research and decision-making processes (Williams, 2018). This sense of responsibility and lack of inclusion in decision-making processes may amplify feelings of anxiety and overwhelm, particularly in the face of inadequate action to combat climate change (Davidson & Freudenburg, 1996). Women are also at greater risk of direct mental health impacts of climate change, as evidenced by higher hospitalization rates during extreme weather events (Basu et al., 2017) and prolonged psychological effects following such events (Alston, 2017). Furthermore, women and non-binary individuals are disproportionately affected by secondary emotional stressors, such as increased intimate partner violence, which has been linked to climate-related weather events (Desai & Zhang, 2021; van Daalen et al., 2020); this has been shown to exacerbate mental health conditions and hinder post-disaster recovery (First et al., 2017).

Although limited research has specifically examined the mental health impacts of climate change on non-binary populations, existing studies highlight important contextual factors. For instance, the discrimination and stigma faced by non-binary individuals and their elevated levels of general psychological distress suggest potential barriers to accessing resources and support to cope with the psychological effects of climate change (Simmonds et al., 2022; Truszczynski et al., 2022). Previous studies also show that non-binary people have higher levels of climate concerns compared to men, along with increased psychological distress and more negative outlooks on the future (Teo et al., 2024). These findings underscore the need for more targeted research to better understand how climate change uniquely affects gender-expansive populations.

Given the potential for a disproportionate impact of climate change across genders, anticipatory worry and anxiety related to climate change may also contribute to disproportionate harm for women and non-binary individuals. While worry can be a normative and adaptive response to the real threat of climate change, clinical perspectives on climate anxiety allow us to examine its more severe

manifestation, such as eco-anxiety and climate-related distress, which may interfere with daily functioning or well-being (Helm et al., 2018; Hogg et al., 2021; Reser et al., 2012). It is important to recognize that climate anxiety, as a legitimate response to a real and pressing global crisis, should not be pathologized, particularly in youth who are responding to an existential threat; pathologizing a response to a significant stressor in climate change moves away from discussing the cause of the distress and risks shifting the blame on to the individual (Thomas et al., 2022). Instead, investigating the clinical dimensions of climate anxiety provides insight into when and how this anxiety escalates to levels that require intervention or support. Previous studies have increasingly investigated the negative mental health effects of climate change in relation to ecological grief (Cunsolo & Ellis, 2018), ecological stress (Helm et al., 2018), eco-anxiety (Hogg et al., 2021), and climate-related distress (Reser et al., 2012). However, relatively few studies have explicitly adopted a gendered perspective on these issues, let alone one that is inclusive of non-binary individuals. Addressing this gap is crucial for understanding how the intersection of gender, mental health, and climate change shapes unique experiences and vulnerabilities.

In the present study, we aim to address this gap in the literature by examining gender differences in climate change anxiety. Climate change anxiety encompasses a range of emotional responses activated by thoughts about the climate, including tension, anxiety, worry, anger, concern, stress, sadness, fear, and depression (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020). We use Clayton and Karazsia's (2020) Climate Change Anxiety Scale (CCAS), which measures cognitive and functional impairments arising from anxiety about climate change (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020). The CCAS has been validated in several countries (e.g., Simon et al., 2022) and is one of the few measures assessing climate anxiety. While the original validation study of the CCAS indicated that there were no significant gender differences when using a binary measure of men and women (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020), understanding how the scale's items perform in relation to gender is critical for research related to gender and climate change. Previous studies, including a French validation of the CCAS by Mougouma-Daouda et al. (2022), have also called for further examination of the scale across gender categories. Therefore, this study also aims to measure whether there is measurement invariance across gender categories, testing metric, scalar and residual invariance.

Our specific hypotheses are as follows: 1) women will report a higher level of climate change anxiety than men; 2) non-binary individuals will report a higher level of climate change anxiety than women and men; and 3) elevated levels of general distress will explain much of the variation of the association between gender and climate change anxiety. We hypothesize that this will be especially true for non-binary respondents, who often face disproportionately high general distress (Aylward et al., 2024). With the inclusion of non-binary respondents in our study, we aim to provide a more inclusive and comprehensive examination of the ways in which gender influences the psychological impacts of climate change. Our findings will inform the development of interventions to support the mental health of individuals across the gender spectrum.

METHODS

Data Collection

This study uses pooled data from three waves of the BC Climate Distress Monitoring System (BC-CDMS), which is an ongoing survey-based study assessing the mental health impacts of climate-related events among individuals residing in British Columbia (BC) (Bratu et al., 2022). Data was collected via an online repeated survey using the SurveyMonkey Platform. Persons living in BC were recruited using paid advertisements on social media platforms. Study one was conducted between May 12th, 2021 and June

21st, 2021; Study two was conducted after the 2021 Pacific Northwest American Heat Dome (between July 15th, 2021 and July 18th, 2021); and Study 3 was conducted after the 2021 Pacific Northwest Atmospheric River and Flooding (between November 30th, 2021 and December 4th, 2021).

Participants were eligible to complete the survey if they were over the age of 16, living in BC, provided informed consent, and were able to complete the survey in English. Participants were further excluded if they had repeated responses over the three waves to maintain the assumption of independence. Further analytic exclusion criteria removed participants with missing outcome (e.g., CCAS), exposure (e.g., gender), or potential confounding variable data.

The BC-CDMS was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Board at Simon Fraser University (Protocol #30000309).

Variables

The main outcome of interest for this study was climate change anxiety (CCA), measured by the CCAS (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020). The CCAS was developed to capture impaired cognitive-emotional involvement with climate change and functional impairment towards climate change. The CCAS was developed and validated using two studies of approximately 200 participants recruited through Amazon's Mechanical Turk. The 13-item CCAS was developed with two sub-scales measuring cognitive and functional impairment, asking participants to rate how often statements (e.g., "I have nightmares about climate change") are true for them using a 5-point Likert-type scale from 'Never' (1) to 'Almost always' (5). The CCAS scale was standardized by dividing the total scale score by the number of items, resulting in a range from 1-5, with higher scores indicating greater CCA. All 13 items are listed in Table 2 by gender. Gender options in the survey include: agender, genderfluid, genderqueer, man, non-binary, trans man, trans woman, and woman. In this study, we use the term non-binary as an umbrella term, encompassing individuals who do not identify with a binary gender, including: agender, genderfluid, genderqueer, and non-binary. Individuals who identify as transgender were included in the gender category that they identify as. Items 1-8 represent cognitive-emotional impairment, and items 9-13 represent functional impairment. As the scale was right-skewed and to ensure the study had a severe value for anxiety to have sufficient sensitivity for our distress measure, we dichotomized CCAS scores into moderate/high (≥ 2) vs. low/no (< 2) CCA. Other studies have also created cutoff measures for the CCAS, with more conservative cutoffs (equivalent to 1.61-1.77) for detecting mild to moderate levels of climate anxiety (Cosh et al., 2024).

Selected confounders included in multivariable analyses included socio-demographic characteristics such as age (16-24; 25-44; 45-65 and 65+), ethnicity (White; Indigenous; Chinese or South Asian; and other), education (Bachelor's degree or graduate training; high school diploma or less; and some advanced training or post-secondary below Bachelor's), income ($< \$30,000$; $\$30,000$ - $\$59,999$; $\$60,000$ - $\$89,999$; $> \$90,000$), and general distress. General distress was explored using the six-item Kessler General Distress Scale (K-6) as a continuous variable (Kessler et al., 2002). The K-6 measures distress in the previous 4 weeks (4-point Likert-type scale, none of the time to all the time, range=0-24, with higher scores indicating greater distress).

Study size

The total pooled sample of eligible respondents was 1704: 74 respondents were excluded due to missing CCAS data, 69 had missing gender data, and 301 had missing data on potential confounding factors, resulting in a final analytic sample of 1260. This can be seen in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Flow chart of sample size

Statistical methods

All statistical analyses were conducted using R version 4.1.2. Descriptive statistics examined gender differences in socio-demographic characteristics, general distress, CCAS scale and sub-scale scores, and responses to all 13 CCAS items using the Chi-square test for categorical variables and the Kruskal-Wallis equality of populations rank test for continuous variables. Spearman's correlation matrices were calculated between the overall CCAS scale, cognitive and functional sub-scale scores, and the K-6 distress scale by gender. All scales in the correlation matrix were continuous variables. Scale reliability was assessed by gender-disaggregated Cronbach's alpha coefficients.

Unadjusted and adjusted logistic regression models explored the independent associations between gender and moderate/high CCAS (vs. no/low). This was done to ensure that our scale was measuring the presence of some to severe climate change anxiety. Two adjusted models assessed

associations between gender and CCAS, with model one adjusting for study wave, age, ethnicity, education, and income, and model two also adjusting for general distress.

Finally, we tested measurement invariance by gender to understand whether and how the CCAS performed. In doing so, we compared three types of measurement invariance: Metric invariance (condition in measurement model equivalence where factor loadings are equal across groups, indicating that the way latent constructs are operationalized by their indicators is consistent), Scalar invariance (stricter level of measurement invariance where, in addition to equal factor loadings, intercepts of the indicators are also equal across groups, suggesting that groups have the same origin point on the latent construct), and Residual invariance (level of measurement model equivalence where, along with equal factor loadings and intercepts, the residuals (or error variances) of the indicators are also equal across groups, indicating uniformity in the measurement error of indicators). CFI cutoffs and thresholds were determined using previous literature (Cheung & Rensvold, 2002).

RESULTS

Descriptive data

In the pooled data, of 1260 complete case respondents, 51.1% identified as men ($n = 631$), 45.9% as women ($n = 578$), and 4.0% ($n = 51$) as non-binary. **Table 1** presents bivariate socio-demographic gender differences. Compared to men, non-binary respondents and women were significantly younger ($p < 0.001$), with 23.5% of non-binary respondents aged 16-24. Bivariate results found significant gender differences in education and income. Men were most likely to have post-secondary training below a Bachelor's degree, and women were most likely to have a Bachelor's degree or higher graduate training ($p < 0.001$). Compared to men, women and non-binary respondents made significantly less income ($p < 0.001$).

Table 1. Bivariate Socio-demographic differences by gender ($n = 1260$)

Variable	Level	Man ($n = 631$)	Non-binary ($n = 51$)	Woman ($n = 578$)	P-value
Survey wave	1	220 (34.9)	24 (47.1)	211 (36.5)	0.455
	2	200 (31.7)	13 (25.5)	169 (29.2)	
	3	211 (33.4)	14 (27.5)	198 (34.3)	
Age group	16-24	71 (11.3)	12 (23.5)	86 (14.9)	<0.001
	25-44	224 (35.5)	30 (58.8)	239 (41.3)	
	45-64	212 (33.6)	9 (17.6)	178 (30.8)	
	65 years and over	124 (19.7)	0 (0.0)	75 (13.0)	
Education	High School or Less	112 (17.7)	14 (27.5)	88 (15.2)	<0.001
	Bachelor's degree or higher	266 (42.2)	27 (52.9)	321 (55.5)	
	Some Post-Secondary Training	253 (40.1)	10 (19.6)	169 (29.2)	
Ethnicity	White	505 (80.0)	38 (74.5)	478 (82.7)	0.263
	Indigenous	28 (4.4)	4 (7.8)	25 (4.3)	
	Other	75 (11.9)	7 (13.7)	47 (8.1)	
	South Asian or Chinese	23 (3.6)	2 (3.9)	28 (4.8)	
Income	Under \$30,000	183 (29.0)	31 (60.8)	278 (48.1)	<0.001
	\$30,000 to \$59,999	159 (25.2)	10 (19.6)	149 (25.8)	
	\$60,000 to \$89,999	134 (21.2)	4 (7.8)	94 (16.3)	
	\$90,000 or more	155 (24.6)	6 (11.8)	57 (9.9)	

Notes: P-values from bivariate analyses using gender and socio-demographic variables. Chi-square tests were used for categorical variables.

Outcome events

Mean overall and sub-scale CCAS scores among non-binary and women respondents (overall = 2.23 [non-binary], 1.94 [women]; cognitive impairment sub-scale = 2.16 [non-binary], 1.95 [women]; functional impairment = 2.33 [non-binary], 1.95 [women]) were significantly higher than men (overall = 1.50; cognitive impairment sub-scale = 1.46; functional impairment = 1.56, $p < 0.001$). Overall, 427 (33.8%) of participants had a CCAS score of two or greater, with men being significantly more likely to have a score of two or greater (22% of men compared to 55% of non-binary respondents and 44% of women, $p < 0.001$).

Table 2 presents gender differences in CCAS responses. Across all 13 CCAS items, there were statistically significant gender differences. Over 50% of men responded 'never' to all items in the CCAS. The item with the largest difference between men and women was "Thinking about climate change makes it difficult for me to concentrate," with 55.8% of men responding never (vs. 19.6% of non-binary respondents and 19.7% of women), followed by "I find myself crying because of climate change" with 80.8% of men stating never (vs. 47.2% of women and 35.3% of non-binary respondents). Across genders, most respondents answered never to the item "I write down my thoughts about climate change and analyze them" (83.8% of men, 66.8% of women, and 62.7% of non-binary respondents) as well as "I think 'why do I react to climate change this way'" with 77.5% of men, 64.5% of women, and 58.8% of non-binary respondents responding never. CCAS reliability was very high for men, women, and non-binary respondents (Cronbach's alpha coefficients = 0.94, 0.94, and 0.92, respectively).

Table 2. CCAS item responses by gender (n = 1260).

CCAS items	Man n (%)	Non-binary n (%)	Woman n (%)	p-value
1. Thinking about climate change makes it difficult for me to concentrate				<0.001
Never (1)	352 (55.8)	10 (19.6)	114 (19.7)	
Rarely (2)	118 (18.7)	5 (9.8)	152 (26.3)	
Somewhat Often (3)	81 (12.8)	20 (39.2)	169 (29.2)	
Often (4)	61 (9.7)	10 (19.6)	99 (17.1)	
Almost always (5)	19 (3.0)	6 (11.8)	44 (7.6)	
2. Thinking about climate change makes it difficult for me to sleep				<0.001
Never (1)	402 (63.7)	15 (29.4)	179 (31.0)	
Rarely (2)	117 (18.5)	11 (21.6)	168 (29.1)	
Somewhat Often (3)	74 (11.7)	13 (25.5)	134 (23.2)	
Often (4)	23 (3.6)	6 (11.8)	73 (12.6)	
Almost always (5)	15 (2.4)	6 (11.8)	24 (4.2)	
3. I have nightmares about climate change				<0.001
Never (1)	497 (78.8)	23 (45.1)	298 (51.6)	
Rarely (2)	82 (13.0)	9 (17.6)	159 (27.5)	
Somewhat Often (3)	32 (5.1)	11 (21.6)	67 (11.6)	
Often (4)	16 (2.5)	4 (7.8)	41 (7.1)	
Almost always (5)	4 (0.6)	4 (7.8)	13 (2.2)	
4. I find myself crying because of climate change				<0.001
Never (1)	510 (80.8)	18 (35.3)	273 (47.2)	
Rarely (2)	77 (12.2)	16 (31.4)	154 (26.6)	

CCAS items	Man n (%)	Non-binary n (%)	Woman n (%)	p-value
Somewhat Often (3)	30 (4.8)	5 (9.8)	89 (15.4)	
Often (4)	12 (1.9)	9 (17.6)	39 (6.7)	
Almost always (5)	2 (0.3)	3 (5.9)	23 (4.0)	
5. I think, "why can't I handle climate change better?"				<0.001
Never (1)	478 (75.8)	22 (43.1)	304 (52.6)	
Rarely (2)	65 (10.3)	9 (17.6)	130 (22.5)	
Somewhat Often (3)	52 (8.2)	12 (23.5)	79 (13.7)	
Often (4)	21 (3.3)	6 (11.8)	39 (6.7)	
Almost always (5)	15 (2.4)	2 (3.9)	26 (4.5)	
6. I go away by myself and think about why I feel this way about climate change				<0.001
Never (1)	472 (74.8)	30 (58.8)	323 (55.9)	
Rarely (2)	79 (12.5)	4 (7.8)	115 (19.9)	
Somewhat Often (3)	43 (6.8)	10 (19.6)	81 (14.0)	
Often (4)	30 (4.8)	6 (11.8)	42 (7.3)	
Almost always (5)	7 (1.1)	1 (2.0)	17 (2.9)	
7. I write down my thoughts about climate change and analyze them				<0.001
Never (1)	529 (83.8)	32 (62.7)	386 (66.8)	
Rarely (2)	43 (6.8)	15 (29.4)	92 (15.9)	
Somewhat Often (3)	33 (5.2)	3 (5.9)	62 (10.7)	
Often (4)	21 (3.3)	1 (2.0)	22 (3.8)	
Almost always (5)	5 (0.8)	0 (0.0)	16 (2.8)	
8. I think, "why do I react to climate change this way?"				<0.001
Never (1)	489 (77.5)	30 (58.8)	373 (64.5)	
Rarely (2)	81 (12.8)	6 (11.8)	126 (21.8)	
Somewhat Often (3)	43 (6.8)	9 (17.6)	47 (8.1)	
Often (4)	14 (2.2)	4 (7.8)	21 (3.6)	
Almost always (5)	4 (0.6)	2 (3.9)	11 (1.9)	
9. My concerns about climate change make it hard for me to have fun with my family or friends				<0.001
Never (1)	436 (69.1)	18 (35.3)	244 (42.2)	
Rarely (2)	98 (15.5)	7 (13.7)	179 (31.0)	
Somewhat Often (3)	59 (9.4)	16 (31.4)	101 (17.5)	
Often (4)	29 (4.6)	8 (15.7)	39 (6.7)	
Almost always (5)	9 (1.4)	2 (3.9)	15 (2.6)	
10. I have problems balancing my concerns about sustainability with the needs of my family				<0.001
Never (1)	383 (60.7)	12 (23.5)	183 (31.7)	
Rarely (2)	87 (13.8)	9 (17.6)	126 (21.8)	
Somewhat Often (3)	82 (13.0)	13 (25.5)	129 (22.3)	
Often (4)	52 (8.2)	11 (21.6)	101 (17.5)	
Almost always (5)	27 (4.3)	6 (11.8)	39 (6.7)	
11. My concerns about climate change interfere with my ability to get work or school assignments done				<0.001
Never (1)	482 (76.4)	20 (39.2)	332 (57.4)	
Rarely (2)	76 (12.0)	14 (27.5)	141 (24.4)	
Somewhat Often (3)	40 (6.3)	11 (21.6)	64 (11.1)	
Often (4)	19 (3.0)	4 (7.8)	24 (4.2)	
Almost always (5)	14 (2.2)	2 (3.9)	17 (2.9)	

CCAS items	Man n (%)	Non-binary n (%)	Woman n (%)	p-value
12. My concerns about climate change undermine my ability to work to my potential				<0.001
Never (1)	472 (74.8)	17 (33.3)	311 (53.8)	
Rarely (2)	70 (11.1)	10 (19.6)	135 (23.4)	
Somewhat Often (3)	40 (6.3)	12 (23.5)	75 (13.0)	
Often (4)	29 (4.6)	11 (21.6)	35 (6.1)	
Almost always (5)	20 (3.2)	1 (2.0)	22 (3.8)	
13. My friends say I think about climate change too much				<0.001
Never (1)	460 (72.9)	27 (52.9)	341 (59.0)	
Rarely (2)	84 (13.3)	8 (15.7)	100 (17.3)	
Somewhat Often (3)	46 (7.3)	9 (17.6)	74 (12.8)	
Often (4)	25 (4.0)	5 (9.8)	35 (6.1)	
Almost always (5)	16 (2.5)	2 (3.9)	28 (4.8)	
Overall CCAS Score	1.50 (0.71)	2.23 (0.88)	1.95 (0.84)	<0.001
CCAS cognitive impairment	1.46 (0.69)	2.16 (0.93)	1.94 (0.86)	<0.001
CCAS functional impairment	1.56 (0.85)	2.33 (0.97)	1.95 (0.92)	<0.001

Notes: P-values from bivariate analyses using the chi-square test for categorical variables and the Kruskal-Wallis test for continuous variables. The variables are gender, the categorical Climate Change Anxiety Survey responses, and the overall and sub-scale CCAS scores.

Table 3 presents overall and gender-disaggregated correlations between the Climate Change Anxiety scale overall, Climate Change Anxiety sub-scales and the Kessler 6-item general distress score.

Table 3. Correlation matrices between the Climate Change Anxiety Scale, Climate Change Anxiety Sub-Scales, and the Kessler General Distress Scale by gender.

Overall				
	K6 stress score	CCAS scores	CCAS cognitive scores	CCAS functional scores
K6 stress score	1			
CCAS scores	0.68	1		
CCAS cognitive scores	0.67	0.97	1	
CCAS functional scores	0.63	0.94	0.84	1
Men				
	K6 stress score	CCAS scores	CCAS cognitive scores	CCAS functional scores
K6 stress score	1			
CCAS scores	0.65	1		
CCAS cognitive scores	0.63	0.95	1	
CCAS functional scores	0.58	0.92	0.8	1
Non-binary				
	K6 stress score	CCAS scores	CCAS cognitive scores	CCAS functional scores
K6 stress score	1			
CCAS scores	0.64	1		
CCAS cognitive scores	0.61	0.95	1	
CCAS functional scores	0.59	0.9	0.74	1
Women				
	K6 stress score	CCAS scores	CCAS cognitive scores	CCAS functional scores
K6 stress score	1			
CCAS scores	0.63	1		
CCAS cognitive scores	0.61	0.97	1	
CCAS functional scores	0.6	0.93	0.82	1

Correlations between general distress scores and CCAS scales and sub-scales ranged from 0.58 (the CCAS functional impairment scale among men) to 0.68 (the CCAS scale overall). Correlations between the CCAS sub-scales and the full scale ranged from 0.74 (the CCAS functional sub-scale correlated with the CCAS cognitive impairment sub-scale among non-binary respondents) to 0.97 (the CCAS scale and cognitive impairment sub-scale overall and among women).

Unadjusted and adjusted logistic regression results

In unadjusted models, women (odds ratio [OR] = 2.86, 95% confidence interval [CI]: 2.23-3.68) and non-binary respondents (OR = 4.35, 95% CI: 2.43-7.85) had significantly greater odds of moderate/high CCAS than men. In models adjusted for age, ethnicity, education, and income, both women (adjusted OR [aOR] = 2.17, 95% CI: 1.65-2.85) and non-binary respondents (aOR = 2.70, 95% CI: 1.43-5.13) still had greater odds of moderate/high CCAS than men, although the effect size was reduced. In model 2 (**Table 4**), where we additionally adjusted for general distress, women continued to have greater odds of moderate/high CCAS (aOR = 1.52, 95% CI: 1.14-2.04) than men; however, the association for non-binary respondents was not statistically significant (aOR = 1.67, 95% CI: 0.86-3.26).

Table 4. Unadjusted and adjusted logistic regression associations between gender and climate anxiety.

Gender group	Unadjusted odds ratio (95% CI)	Adjusted odds ratio (95% CI) ¹	Adjusted odds ratio (95% CI) ²
Men (ref)	1.00	1.00	1.00
Women	2.86 (2.23-3.68)	2.17 (1.65-2.85)	1.52 (1.14-2.04)
Non-binary	4.35 (2.43-7.85)	2.70 (1.43-5.13)	1.67 (0.86-3.26)

Notes: ¹Adjusted for wave, age, ethnicity, education, and income ²Adjusted for wave, age, ethnicity, education, income, and general distress

Measurement Invariance

In addition to examining the relationship between gender and CCAS, we compared three types of measurement invariance: Metric invariance (a condition in measurement model equivalence where factor loadings are equal across groups, indicating that the way latent constructs are operationalized by their indicators are consistent), Scalar invariance (stricter level of measurement invariance where, in addition to equal factor loadings, intercepts of the indicators are also equal across groups, suggesting that groups have the same origin point on the latent construct), and Residual invariance (level of measurement model equivalence where, along with equal factor loadings and intercepts, the residuals (or error variances) of the indicators are also equal across groups, indicating uniformity in the measurement error of indicators). For Metric Invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = 0.0020$), we observed a ΔCFI value below the threshold of 0.01, indicating that the model's factor loadings are invariant across the groups being studied. This implies that the underlying constructs (e.g., "cognitive," "functional") are measured in a similar manner across the different gender groups. For Scalar Invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = 0.0147$), we observed a ΔCFI value exceeding the 0.01 threshold, suggesting a lack of scalar invariance across groups. This indicates that there are group-level differences in the intercepts (or averages) of the items. For residual Invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = 0.0170$), we observed a ΔCFI value above the 0.01 threshold, pointing to a lack of residual invariance. This implies that the items in our model have different amounts of error or unique variances when applied to different gender groups.

DISCUSSION

Primary Findings

Our results indicate that women and non-binary respondents had significantly higher climate change anxiety than men. However, the extent of the gender differences in CCA differed across scale items. Also, this effect was largely explained by levels of general psychological distress, particularly for non-binary respondents who had significantly higher general distress levels than men and women. In all models, women had a greater likelihood of moderate/high CCAS levels compared to men. Items with the greatest differences in responses ('never' to 'almost always') between men and women affected cognitive function, including impacting respondents' concentration and crying due to climate change, whereas the greatest item response differences between non-binary respondents and men were related to respondents' functional ability to get work or school done. Assessments of measurement invariance in the CCAS indicated metric invariance (suggesting consistent measurement in underlying constructs) but not scalar or residual invariance (indicating differences in item intercepts and error variances between gender groups).

Relationship to Previous Studies

The CCAS has been validated by previous studies in various contexts, including in Poland (Larionow et al., 2022), France (Mouguiama-Daouda et al., 2022), and Italy (Innocenti et al., 2021). However, only Larionow et al. (2022) examined gender differences, with the results showing configural, metric, and scalar invariance across gender categories. Similar to other studies conducted in high-income settings, CCA in our sample was relatively low (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020; Wullenkord et al., 2021), and women had greater CCA than men (Wullenkord et al., 2021). While general psychological distress explained much of the variability in the association between gender and CCA for non-binary participants, this was driven by the extremely high levels of general psychological distress reported by non-binary participants. Thus, findings exploring differences in CCA need to be further explored with larger samples using critical feminist and queer theory understandings of how gender processes such as gender socialization, embodiment, and relations influence men, women, and non-binary individuals' emotional responses to stressors (Matud, 2004), like climate change. Gender differences in CCAS scores may be explained by gender differences in emotional regulation. For example, women were much more likely than men to report maladaptive emotional regulations such as rumination (constantly talking or thinking about climate change), which aligns with prior research on gender differences in emotional regulation (Nolen-Hoeksema, 2012). Also, adaptive emotional regulation strategies captured in the CCAS, such as problem-solving (e.g., thinking through why one reacts a certain way to change) and reappraisal (e.g., writing down and analyzing thoughts), have been found to offset the negative effects of maladaptive emotional responses among women but not men (McLean et al., 2011). Men, however, are less likely to use traditional emotional regulation strategies (e.g., seeking social support, crying) (McLean et al., 2011; Nolen-Hoeksema, 2012). Thus, emotional regulation strategies more often used by men, such as alcohol (Danielson et al., 2024), or those that are more unconscious, may not be fully captured in the CCAS, which may partially explain some of the gender differences observed in our study.

Beyond emotional regulation, gender differences in CCAS item responses are likely linked to the social factors (e.g., unequal distribution of labour, wealth, and power across gender axes) that produce and reproduce gender stratification and nonconformity. For example, higher CCAS among women may be due to gender roles and norms, whereby women most often assume caregiving roles and thus may face elevated stressors of supporting and comforting children and elders under their care, along with their own stress and anxiety surrounding climate change (Hoogeveen et al., 2021).

Inequitable divisions of power, wealth, and labour (e.g., caregiving responsibilities) result in high levels of gender discrimination and stigma and contribute to excess mental health burdens among women and non-binary folks (McLean et al., 2011; Valentine & Shipherd, 2018). Among women, studies have demonstrated that gender roles surrounding caregiving and unequal division of labour, particularly unpaid labour in the home, lead to heightened distress, impacting sleep and concentration, all of which are elements measured within the CCAS (Burgard, 2011). Gendered inequities in wealth and the feminization of poverty are well documented (Belle, 1990) and evident in our data, whereby men were significantly more likely to make $\geq \$90,000$ /year despite women having greater education levels. Greater socio-economic status among men may further contribute to low levels of perceived threats from climate change (Marshall et al., 2006), which may help to explain the relatively low levels of CCA reported by men in our study.

While the gender differences in our results remained even after adjusting for income and education, it is important to note that societal gender inequities that impact women and non-binary individuals likely have a residual effect on mental health, including levels of anxiety and emotional responses to climate change, regardless of income. Gender inequities, such as gender discrimination, are a known determinant of depression and anxiety, especially for individuals who may deviate from gender norms and perform outside of the gender binary (Valentine & Shipherd, 2018). Internalized stigma related to gender identity has been linked to heightened distress among LGBTQ+ individuals, with the potential to disproportionately impact sleep and increase night terrors and, in turn, daytime concentration when compared to cisgender individuals (Levenson et al., 2020). Poor sleep, lack of time sleeping, and struggling to concentrate are likely compounded for non-binary respondents compared to women and men and may help to explain why non-binary respondents score higher than men on all items in the CCAS. However, unlike women, general distress explained most of the variability in CCA among non-binary respondents. While the confidence interval for non-binary participants contained the null value, after adjusting for general psychological distress, the effect remained positive. The finding of a lack of statistical significance could be driven by inadequate power, warranting further investigation in larger samples.

Implications

Understanding how women, men, and non-binary individuals negatively (e.g., anxiety, anger, fear) and positively (e.g., hope, resilience) respond to climate change can improve and inform gender-targeted and transformative public health efforts aimed at shifting societal norms, resources, and power dynamics that perpetuate gender inequities in experiences of climate change anxiety and distress. Gender-sensitive, responsive, and transformative measures to assess climate change-related distress will be necessary to ensure that gender-transformative efforts to support communities and individuals most affected by negative emotional and psychosocial reactions to climate change are appropriate, acceptable, and successful across all genders (Martin et al., 2020).

Our assessment of measurement invariance revealed that while the CCAS exhibits metric invariance across men, women, and non-binary individuals, scalar and residual invariance were not supported. This indicates that, although the construct of climate change anxiety is understood similarly (i.e., factor loadings are stable) across these groups, there may be systematic differences in how participants from different gender identities use the response scales (different item intercepts) or in the item-level measurement error. As a result, direct comparisons of total CCAS scores (e.g., mean differences across gender groups) should be interpreted with caution.

From a practical standpoint, these findings underscore the importance of (a) critically examining whether the scale items capture the diverse ways that climate distress manifests and (b) recognizing

that the same numerical score may reflect different degrees or expressions of anxiety depending on one's gender. Consequently, further studies, especially those that include larger samples of non-binary individuals and use mixed methods, may wish to investigate which CCAS items are most sensitive or potentially biased for particular gender groups. Identifying and addressing such bias through partial measurement invariance testing or item modification can lead to improved accuracy and fairness in assessing climate change anxiety. Ultimately, continued scale development and validation will help ensure that interventions, policy decisions, and academic research stemming from CCAS measurements can appropriately support the distinct experiences of climate anxiety across the gender spectrum.

Limitations

While findings support that there are important differences in the ways in which CCA is experienced across genders, including non-binary individuals who are often excluded from gender-based analyses, there are several limitations to this study that should be noted. Our analysis of gender differences in responses to the individual items on the CCAS suggests that there may be gaps in accurately measuring CCA for different genders. This paper attempts to describe, theorize, and explain differences in CCA across genders; however, there are likely more differences within genders, given that gender categories themselves are transient and diverse. Future qualitative research is needed to explore intersectional experiences of climate change and subsequent mental health impacts within and across genders. Specifically, while targeted efforts were made to recruit a diverse sample of respondents (e.g., advertisements picturing ethnically diverse populations), most respondents across all three waves of data were white, Western, educated, industrialized, rich, and democratic (WEIRD) (Henrich et al., 2010), limiting our ability to explore intersectional CCA differences. The results of our study should thus not be interpreted outside of WEIRD contexts, such as Canada. Also, this study had a relatively high exclusion rate of 25%, which may introduce bias and limit generalizability. This study recruited participants through randomly distributed advertisements on social media channels, thus only recruiting participants who had social media. The research team does not have control over how ads were displayed to platform users, nor did we collect data on participants who were not formally enrolled in the survey. We also provided informed consent and, therefore, cannot ascertain or report any information about the recruitment. We acknowledge that online recruitment processes are beyond the researcher's control and may change over time according to the decisions of the advertising platform. Given the topic of the survey, the sample was likely biased towards respondents who had strong opinions about the subject matter and thus may not be generalizable to all British Columbians. There was no explicit process to prevent bots or repeat responses; however, the SurveyMonkey platform does use location and IDs to prevent multiple responses. Additionally, the survey includes a screening question regarding whether participants had filled the survey out before; participants who have would not be included. However, participants may have misreported that question.

Future Research

Our study highlights the potential value of exploring mediating and moderating factors underlying the gendered impacts of climate change and climate change anxiety. Future studies should examine potential pathways that may contribute to disproportionate mental health impacts. These factors may include further exploring gender constructs such as gender roles, relations, and identity and how constructs, directly and indirectly, relate to climate anxiety as well as generalized psychological distress. Qualitative and quantitative studies can be synthesized to isolate these effects, and community-based research methods can support appropriate climate-related mitigation and adaptation strategies that

can help to control the disproportionate harms experienced by women and non-binary people, as well as the unique stressors faced by individuals across the gender spectrum.

CONCLUSION

Our study found significant differences in climate change anxiety between men, women, and non-binary respondents in British Columbia, Canada. Much of the gender differences in CCA may be explained by how CCA has been measured, with findings highlighting the need to further explore the ways in which men may be differentially experiencing and responding to climate change and climate-related events (e.g., substance use, anger, violence) that may not be captured in current measures of climate change anxiety and distress. Thus, this study area warrants additional qualitative research to unpack specific gendered emotional responses to climate change, including climate change-related coping strategies. Gender differences in CCA may also be explained by larger societal structures that drive gender inequity and, in turn, distress for women and non-binary folks. These differences highlight the importance of targeting gender-sensitive and transformative mental health supports that are not only tailored to the unique needs of men, women, and non-binary people but further address multileveled gender inequities that heighten distress and fuel climate change-related burdens and anxieties for women and non-binary individuals.

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AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research

committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. Each study conducted as part of the BC-CDMS was reviewed and approved by the research ethics board at Simon Fraser University (Protocol #30000309).

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Not applicable.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The Authors declare they have no competing interests.

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